

acceptable grain shape and quality. Anther culture through doubled-haploid breeding could help achieve these objectives.

In Egypt, saline areas represent more than 30% of the total rice-growing area. Five crosses for these areas were selected to study callus and plant regeneration efficiencies and to get homozygous lines tolerant of salinity. The cross combinations were japonica//indica/japonica (crosses 1 and 2); indica/japonica//japonica (cross 3); and indica/japonica//indica/japonica (crosses 4 and 5).

Anthers were plated in media routinely used in the IRRI tissue culture laboratory, three for callus induction and eight for plant regeneration.

On average, the L8 medium induced the highest rate of calli (Table 1). Highest callus induction rates were in Giza 159/C732048 (32.3%) and Agami M-1/C731135 (28.3%). These crosses have japonica female parents. Efficiency-

Table 2. Percentage and number of green plants produced in 8 plant regeneration media for 5 F₁ crosses. IRRI, 1990 DS.

Cross	Green plant regeneration frequency (%)								Calli producing green plants	
	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	SK-11	no.	% ^a
Giza 159/C732048	0.4	1.7	5.4	2.3	1.3	0.6	1.4	2.1	32	2.0
Agami M-1/C731135	0.9	0.6	1.0	0.7	0.7	1.4	1.2	2.9	10	1.0
GZ1368-5-4/Niigatawase	0.7	1.7	4.2	6.3	2.0	2.0	0	0	19	1.5
GZ1368-5-4/C731135	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.0	0	1	2.0
GZ2447S-17/C732048	0	0	0	6.3	4.0	2.2	1.2	0	8	2.0
Calli producing green plants (no.)	3	9	18	16	5	6	6	7	70	
Average ^a (%)	0.8	1.2	2.3	2.4	1.2	1.3	0.9	1.3		1.6

^a Total calli producing green plants / Total calli plated for regeneration × 100

cies were lower in crosses with indica/japonica parents (GZ1368-5-4 and GZ2447S-17).

For plant regeneration, eight media differing in kinetin (Kin), indole-acetic acid (IAA), and naphthaleneacetic acid (NAA) concentrations were used. Green plant regeneration efficiency was

generally low (Table 2). The M3 and M4 media gave the highest regeneration percentages. M3 has 5 mg Kin and 1 mg IAA/liter; M4 has 2 mg Kin and 1 mg NAA/liter. Plant regeneration capacity of the media varied according to genotype. A total of 325 plants were regenerated from 70 calli. □

Interaction of media for callus induction and for plant regeneration in rice anther culture

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The response of a genotype grown in vitro depends to a large extent on the composition of the culture medium. Usually, callus induction is in a medium different from that for plant regeneration. This makes it important to identify the best combination of media for tissue culture.

We plated anthers of five F₁ rice crosses bred for Egyptian conditions on three callus induction media and eight plant regeneration media. The callus induction media G1, Fj, and L8 differed in their basal composition as well as in hormone concentrations. The basal medium of Fj is B5, that of L8 is N6, that of G1 is a combination of B5 and MS. Respectively, G1, Fj, and L8, have 0.75, 0.5, and 2 mg kinetin (Kin)/liter; 2.0, 0.5 mg of 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D)/liter; and 2.5, 2.5, and 3.5

Table 1. Callus induction efficiency of 5 F₁ crosses in 3 callus induction media.

Cross	Callus induction ^a (%)			Average ^b (%)
	G1	Fj	L8	
Nahda/Milyang 85	13.48	38.79	50.79	34.55
Giza 14/Milyang 85	36.50	38.97	58.60	44.38
Giza 159/C732048	38.50	29.10	37.80	35.55
Giza 171/C731135	45.60	35.10	37.50	40.00
GZ2175-5-3/C731135	27.80	41.30	25.64	30.61
Average (%) ^b	32.40	36.67	42.06	
LSD (crosses) 0.05 = ns. 0.01 = ns				
LSD (media) 0.05 = 1.67. 0.01 = 2.20				

^a Six hundred anthers per cross were plated on each medium.

^b Total anthers with calli / Total anthers plated × 100

mg of naphthaleneacetic acid (NAA)/liter.

The basal medium for plant regeneration was Murashige and Skoog's. Kinetin concentrations (mg/liter) differ for M1, M2, M3, M4, M5, M6, M7, and SK-11: 1, 10, 5, 2, 4, 8, 16, and 1, respectively. All the media have 1 mg NAA/l except M3, which has 1 mg indole 3-acetic acid (IAA)/l instead of NAA. SK-11 also includes benzylamino purine (1mg/liter) and casein hydrolysate (500 mg/liter).

In callus induction, there was a significant interaction between crosses and media, and significant differences among the three media (Table 1).

Table 2. Interaction between callus induction medium and plant regeneration medium in anther culture of 5 cross combinations.

Callus induction medium	Green plants (%) from regeneration medium								Total (no.)	Av (%) ^a
	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	SK-11		
G1	1.8	2.3	4.8	1.4	4.3	1.8	5.8	2.4	79	2.9
Fj	0.9	0.7	2.5	3.5	2.0	1.8	3.6	3.6	58	2.2
L8	3.0	4.5	4.9	4.3	4.5	4.1	2.9	5.1	108	4.1
Total no.	16	30	43	31	26	29	35	35	245	
Av (%) ^a	3.0	1.8	2.4	4.1	3.0	3.1	3.9	2.8		3.3

^a Total calli producing green plants / Total calli plated for regeneration × 100

The interaction between callus induction and plant regeneration media is shown in Table 2. Calli produced in G1 medium could be regenerated on either M3, M5, or M7 regeneration media. Calli produced in Fj should be regener-

ated on M4, M7, or SK-11; those produced in L8 should be regenerated on M2, M3, M4, M5, or SK-11. The highest percentages of green plants were produced on M4 and M7. ■

Hybrid rice yield trials in the Mekong Delta

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We compared seven IRRI-bred rice hybrids and two check varieties in 1990 wet (WS) and dry (DS) seasons. Twenty-day-old seedlings were transplanted at 20 × 15-cm spacing, in a randomized complete block design with three replications.

Yield performance of F₁ rice hybrids in Vietnam, 1990-91.

Cross	Duration (d)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Filled grains (no/panicle)	1000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)	Standard heterosis (%)
<i>1990 wet season^a</i>						
IR58025 A/IR29723-143-3-2-1 R	125	429 abc	118.6 a	28.0	7.6 a	+41.83
IR62429 A/IR29723-143-3-2-1 R	116	396 abc	92.4 cde	26.6	6.7 b	+26.26
IR58025 A/IR9761-19-1 R	106	407 abcd	111.0 ab	28.8	6.0 bc	+16.40
IR62829 A/IR9761-19-1 R	106	473 a	97.3 bc	25.0	5.9 bcd	+13.89
IR62829 A/IR24 R	113	451 ab	80.0 bc	27.2	5.6 cd	+5.62
V20 A/IR9761-19-1 R	104	418 abc	96.0 bc	28.0	5.5 cd	+6.75
V20 A/Milyang 46 R	104	352 cd	87.6 e	30.4	5.4 cd	+4.42
MTL 58 (check)	120	369 bcd	89.0 cde	26.0	5.3 cd	
MTL 61 (check)	104	334 d	83.6 cde	22.6	5.2 d	
CV (%)		11.80	8.14			
<i>1990-91 dry season</i>						
IR62829 A/IR29723-143-3-2-1 R	100	14	107.6	23.8	6.67	+17.02
IR62829 A/IR9761-19-1 R	99	12	99.7	21.1	5.70	+5.60
IR58025 A/IR29723-143-3-2-1 R	107	13	113.1	24.9	5.40	
IR58025 A/IR9761-19-1 R	99	13	94.7	22.5	4.87	
IR62829 A/IR24 R	99	11	86.6	22.7	3.93	
V20 A/IR9761-19-1 R	87	11	85.2	24.7	3.40	
V20 A/Milyang 46 R	89	12	82.5	27.5	3.00	
OM576 (check)	101	13	103.4	24.0	5.40	
MTL 58 (check)	105	12	95.9	24.2	5.70	
cv (%)			10.0		5.4	
LSD (0.05)			14.5		0.40	
LSD (0.01)			14.5		0.53	

^aIn a column, yields followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Surveys of disease or insect incidence/severity in one environment are useful only if the information is related to other variables (e.g., climatic factors, crop intensification, cultivars, management practices, etc.). By itself, information on incidence in one environment does not increase scientific knowledge.

Yield potential

Performance of different height rice lines under intermediate deep water levels

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We evaluated 12 promising rice lines with different plant heights (semidwarf, semitall, and tall) and growth durations (90-180 d), and N level (0 and 40 kg N/ha) under intermediate deep water (up to 80 cm) during 1988. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with three replications, with rice cultivars in the main plot and N level in 15.8-m² subplots.

Experimental lines were direct seeded in dry soil 6 Jun, at 400 seeds/m² with 20-cm row spacing, and fertilized basally with 9 kg P and 17 kg K/ha. Germination was good.

Water in the field increased gradually from mid-Jun, to 76 cm on 10 Aug and 83 cm on 25 Sep. During most of the crop growth period, water level was 30-60 cm. Water receded gradually from early Oct. The crops matured in mid-Dec.

Application of N increased plant height and yield attributes significantly (see table). The four tall cultivars had significantly higher yields. They elongated faster as water level rose and flowered during the first week of Nov.

Grain yield decreased linearly with decreasing plant height, and the three semidwarfs had very low yields. Popular, short-duration upland cultivar Kalinga 3 virtually failed under deep water. Although this variety had panicle numbers similar to those of other varieties, its panicle size was considerably reduced, partly because of seed germination of matured panicles lying on the water surface and partly because of damage by birds after early maturity.

Local semitall cultivar Hathipanja had the highest 1000-grain weight but had